

Table 1: List of abbreviations, acronyms, initialisms used in the paper “Practical Challenges of Value Stream Mapping in Software-Defined Vehicle Development”

Short	Expanded	Explanation
3L5Y	Three-legged Five-whys	A structured root cause analysis methodology used to solve complex problems by drilling down into three distinct areas: Occurrence, Detection, and Systemic causes.
A-CPS	Automotive Cyber-Physical system	A tightly integrated network of sensors, actuators, embedded processors/microcontrollers and communication links that jointly monitor, control, and communicate vehicle functions, turning a car into a real-time, data-driven, cyber-physical entity
CPU	Central Processing Unit	A CPU is the primary hardware component that implements at a minimum a fetch-decode-execute cycle, and execute machine-code within its core.
C-State	Current State	Current state (map): a visual diagram that captures how a process or system generates value
CPS	Cyber-Physical System	An integrated system that couples computational components(sensors, actuators, controllers, software) with physical process allowing real time interaction (reason, understand, control) with the physical world.
ECU	Electronics Control Unit	An ECU is an embedded system that may use sensors, and/or actuators to perform a coordinated activity in a vehicle context
KPI	Key Performance Indicator	A KPI is a quantifiable metric that measures status towards a goal, enabling stakeholders to assess performance.
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer	An OEM is a company that designs, builds and sells a finished vehicle under its own brand.
OTA	Over-The-Air	Over-the-air (updates): Getting updates from a remote service using the telematics unit using radio (e.g. 4/5/6G/wifi/etc.)
PDVSM	Product Development VSM	Value stream mapping focused on product development activities [?]
R&D	Research and Development	The organizational function which systematically pursues new knowledge and its practical application to create or optimize products, processes or technologies
SDV	Software-Defined Vehicle(s)	A vehicle whose functions, features and behavior are primarily configured and controlled by software, instead of an immutable hardware-centric design
VSM	Value Stream mapping	A lean tool that creates a visual diagram of all steps that contribute to a value generating activity
V&V	Verification and Validation	The systematic process of checking that a product is built correctly (verification) and that it meets the intended purpose (validation)
uC	microcontroller	A hardware component that has control functions and contains a micro-processor. A small embedded computer that can be used to control digital and analog signals, perform computations, may access network, memory, flash, etc.